

A Comparative Study of Stress of Facebook Users and Non Users

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the present study was to compare the level of stress of face book users and non users. A sample of 80 subjects [age ranged 19-22 years] was taken Gurukul Kangri University, Haridwar. Each group consisted of 40 subjects. Experimental task was given to measure stress level. Quota sampling technique was used for selection of the sample. Stress scale developed by M. Singh was used to measure the stress level of participants. Chi-square test was used to analyses the obtained data. Result revealed that face book users were found to be more stressful than non users. During the briefing of research following have been found accountable for high level of stress in face book users some of the factors are such that-

- In the race of gaining more and more “likes.”
- Messed situation due to lots of people “messaging” same time.
- Due to over consciousness for “comments” on face book account “wall.”
- Peer pressure of own impressive signature expression.

These findings draw the attention of the researcher towards finding the new kind of stress management techniques for face book users.

Keywords: Facebook & Mental stress.

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INTRODUCTION

Face book has become a daily life tool in the world of the 21st century. It's a modern era that means the age of the competition, specialization and of the researches. There is a rapid progress in every field as education, business, management, political system, in the scientific concept and in the technical system also. And in this fast running life every one run with the crowd and no one think or aware about their inner potential. Due to this lack of awareness, many of the people suffers with the mental and emotional disorder as inferiority, guilt, low self esteem, lack of confidence, lack of insight and mental stress also. Mental stress in a limit is good for a person, it motivates us to do some thing new but if it increases day by day then we can suffer with a mental problem that is mental stress.

Simply we can say that “stress slowly kills you while it informs you that you are still alive.” Stress is a term that is commonly used today but has become increasingly difficulty to define. Our work is one of the top cause of mental stress. If we are experiencing stress, the mind gets affected. The train of thoughts becomes distorted. Some experience a mental black out or what people mean when they say “the mind is blank” concentration is affected when we experience mental stress. When we feel mentally stressed out, we lose our logical and rational manner of thinking that is why some people would probably tell you that you are not in your “right mind.” This is what happens when the mind is pressured and tensed.

According to Selye [1] in his book *The Stress of life*, “Stress refers to nonspecific response of the body to any demand made upon it.” At last we can say that “stress is a the downside of awareness and the upside of action.”

In present era, Face book has become an inseparable part of one's life especially among youth. Now-a-day it become a trend that is not only in leisure period but in working hours also people prefer to be in face book or other social networking site rather than interacting with near by social situations. It is not bad to use these sites but it become worse when children, teenagers always remain indulge in these resulting their automatic cut off from the society and increase mental illness.

Many researches have proved that many face book users, who spends lots of time in face book world, have been found to avoid to spoil their real life relations or have been found to avoid the works. Thus all these changes in their normal behavior. Face book is an online social networking service, whose name stems from the colloquial name from the

book given to the student at the start of the academic year by some university administration in the united states to help student get to know each other. Sarah [2] wrote "A brief history of Facebook" Mark Zuckerberg with his college roommate and follow harward university student. As of July 2011 face book has more than 800 million active users. User may create a personal profile add other users as friends and exchange messages, including automatic notifications when they update their profile. Face book users must register before using the site. "Face book users with more friends suffer more stress and neurotic limbo from feeling they have to continually update and amuse their larger audiences according University of Edinburgh [3]. "A large member of friend on face book may appear impressive but according to a news report, the more social circles a person is linked to online the more likely social media will be a source of stress."

Objectives: To see the relationship between facebook users and non users on the level of stress.

Hypothesis: There will be no significant relation between facebook users and non users on the level of stress.

Material & Method:

Sample:- 80 male and female students of Gurukul Kangri Vishwavidhyalya are constitutes sample of the study. The age of the subject is 19 to 22 years. The subject are taken by the quota sampling.

Tool:- Researcher used Stress Scale which is developed by Dr. M. Singh [4].

Variable:- Facebook as a independent variable & Stress as a dependent variable in present study.

Result:- Researcher record the result obtained from the statistical analysis of responses with the help of chi-square test. According to table E the result is significant on 0.01 level. That means of hypothesis has rejected.

	High conformity	Average conformity	Low conformity
Face book users	0	14	25
Non-users	12	26	2

Chi-square- 38.7
df= 2
p- Significant at 0.01 level

DISCUSSION AND INTERPRETATION

Present investigation is to compare the stress level of face book users and non users. 80 sample are selected for this dissertation work. Face book is an online social networking service, whose name stems from the colloquial name for the book given to the student at the start of the academic year by some university administrations in the united states to help students get to know each other. Face book now allows any users who declare them selves to be at least 13 years old to become registered users of the sites. Users must register before using the site after which they may create a personal profile add other users as friends and exchange messages, including automatic notifications when they update their profile. There is no doubt that all of your friends are registered on social network called face book. Face book is considered to be the biggest social network on the internet.

At the moment face book contains nearly 10 million abusers with face book you can find people and communicate with them as well as share photos and videos on top of this usage of face book for business networking becomes popular with many people. Through this study we want to know how face book effect on stress level. Second variable which we have used in this study is mental stress which means mental stress is a person's to a stressor such as an environmental condition or a stimulus. Stress is a body's method of reacting to a challenge. According to the stressful event, the body's way to respond to stress is by sympathetic nervous system activation which results in the fight or flight response. Stress typically describes a negative condition or a positive condition that can have an impact on a person's mental stress and physical well-being.

Hens selye [5] a model diving stress into eustress and distress where stress enhances function(physical or mental, such as through strength training or challenging work), it may be considered eustress. Persistent stress that is not resolved through coping or adaptation, deemed distress, may lead to anxiety or withdrawal (depression) behavior. Before beginning of this study I have constructed a null hypothesis- There is no significance difference between face book and mental stress after this study I have seen that there is no difference between face book and mental stress for this study I have selected 80 sample (40 face book users and 40 non users). I have used stress scale which was developed by Dr. M. Singh.

After collection of data statistical analysis was done by chi-square method and I have collected a reliable score where chi-square is 38.7 and I saw this score in table E and it is significant at 0.01 level this means my null hypothesis has rejected and my result revealed that face book and social networks in general, could be a new source of psychological stress. Other experts said stress is well known factor in asthma attacks. Very often it is found that face book or internet users are addicted to it. Now a days face book has become inevitable part of our lives which to some extent imposing negative impact on us. Most distressing part is that school going children are using it very much resulting in their declined class performance and grades.

There are so many researches and studies that represent face book users with more friends suffer more stress. Boyd & Ellison [6] suggested that increasing your friends count on this giant social networking site can also increase levels of stress, particularly if your acquaintances originate from different social groups. Doctors seeing unexplainable asthma attacks in patients should consider the stress brought on through social networking sites. Dr. Kathy Charles, who led the study said, "we found it was actually those with the most contacts, those who had invested the most time in the site, who were the ones most likely to be stressed [7]. Five doctors have written to the lancet to documents the case of an 18 year old asthmatic man whose condition was stable until he split up with his girlfriend and she erased him from her face book page.

There was also an online survey component that attracted 175 participants (127 female and 48 male with a mean age of 30.4 year) which found that:-

- 12 percent of respondents said that face book made them feel anxious of these, respondents had an average of 117 friends each, who said that face book did not make them feel anxious, had an average of 75 friends each.
- 63 percent delayed replying to friend requests.
- 32 percent said rejecting friend requests led to feeling of guilt and discomfort.
- 10 percent admitted disliking receiving friend requests.

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We may feel that we have friend. But the feelings are some what tangled and we know what we have is virtual friends. They are not going to be there when we feel low. There is no one to pat our back or give a hug. After this while we feel stressed out become we feel we have to respond back.

CONCLUSION

In the last my research can be concluded on the basis of interpretation that due to living in virtual world face book users and social networks in general, could be a new source of psychological stress. If you find yourself constantly logging on to face book or browsing for hours at time, you may be setting yourself up for poor mental health. Researchers at the university of Gothenburg found that those who constantly use a computer or their mobile phone can develop stress, sleeping disorder and depression and other mental illnesses. The average user spend 75 minutes per day on face book. The average user logs on to face book 6.1 times per day.70% log in every time they start their computer or web reader. 26% feel ill at ease if they do not get to log in regularly. Women spend on average 81 minutes per day on face book. Men spend on average 64 minutes per day on face book.

After administration of the scale and results obtained are showing that the null hypothesis which was formulated for measuring the mental stress level is significant at 0.01 level of confidence.

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